

Distributed GIS Based Decision Support System For Efficiency Evaluation Of Education System: A Case Study Of Primary School Education System Of Bundelkhand Zone, Uttar Pradesh, India

Authors : Garima Srivastava,R.K.Srivastava, R.C.Vaishya

Abstract : Decision Support System (DSS), a query-based system meant to help decision makers to use a variety of information for decision making, plays a very vital role in sustainable growth of any country. For this very purpose it is essential to analyze the educational system because education is the only way through which people can be made aware as to how to sustain our planet. The purpose of this paper is to prepare a decision support system for efficiency evaluation of education system with the help of Distributed Geographical Information System.

Keywords : Distributed GIS, Web GIS, Spatial Decision Support System, Bundelkhand Zone, Efficiency, Primary School Education.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014